

This is the performance on different meshes. This is on the GTX 3090 GPU with Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-1650 v4 @ 3.60GHz. This gives the following speed up wrt the state-of-the-art ("GPU-based real-time soft tissue deformation with cutting and haptic feedback"). For the larger liver mesh (1.6M tetrahedra), our running time per tetrahedron is 0.00002 ms. For the 3874 tetrahedral mesh reported by the state-of-the-art paper, the same is $64 \text{ ms} / 3874 = 0.01652039 \text{ ms}$. The peak FLOPS of their Nvidia GTX 285 GPU is 88.56 GFLOPS. The peak FLOPS performance of GTX 3090 is 35.58 TFLOPS, which is 404 times GTX 285. Now, one tetrahedron is getting processed 826.02X faster on our machine. Since $826/404 = 2.04$, our algorithm is actually more efficient than the state-of-the-art.